

Austroglanis gilli Clanwilliam catfish

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Bony Fish

Size: 13.7 cm SL (male)

Distribution:

The Clanwilliam catfish is endemic to the Olifants-Doring River System in the Western Cape, South Africa.

Importance:

This small freshwater catfish is found in only one river system in the world. It is listed by the IUCN as Near Threatened. It grows slowly, reaching maturity at about three years, and is vulnerable to changes in its environment.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 46.34 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 4.9 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.73 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.2% [Single: 96.1%, Duplicated: 3.1%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 2 611.29 kilobases

Contig number: 3 103

DIPLOMICS
CONNECTING RESEARCHERS & WORLD CLASS OMICS FACILITIES

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